

pH-metric and electronic spectral measurements on the mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) containing unsubstituted imidazole and some dipeptides

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CuAB, CuABH₁, CuA₂B or CuA₂BH₁ mixed ligand complexes have been identified in the Cu^{II}-imidazole (A)-glycyl-L-phenylalanine, L-phenylalanylglycine, glycyl-L-tyrosine, L-tyrosylglycine, L-phenylalanyl-L-tyrosine and L-tyrosyl-L-phenylalanine (B) systems. The stability constant values indicate the monodentate binding of imidazole (A) and bidentate binding of the dipeptide (B) ligands in the CuAB and CuA₂B complexes. Both the pH-metric and electronic spectral results demonstrate the tridentate mode of binding of (BH₁) in CuABH₁. However, in the CuA₂BH₁ species tridentate mode of binding of (BH₁) exists only to an appreciable extent.

Considerable attention has been paid in recent years¹⁻⁴ on the study of the coordination chemistry of peptides with metal ions. The initial complex formation between a peptide and a metal ion in the binary and mixed ligand complex systems results in a chelate involving *N*-amino and *O*-peptide atoms⁴. At higher pH values, peptide undergoes deprotonation of the amide group and in the binary systems it binds via *N*-amino, *N*-peptide and *O*-carboxylato groups. The structures and stability constants of Cu^{II} complexes of dipeptides composed of *N*-terminal arginine, lysine or glycinate and *C*-terminal aspartate, glutamate or glycinate have been investigated recently⁵. In the mixed ligand complex systems depending on the nature of other ligand involved in coordination, the coordination tendency of the

dipeptide ligand changes – in some cases it binds in a bidentate mode via *N*-amino and *N*-peptide atoms^{4,6} and in some other cases via *N*-amino, *N*-peptide and *O*-carboxylato atoms^{7,8}. By considering the fact that phenylalanine gains importance since it is converted into tyrosine by phenylalanine hydroxylase and tyrosine constitutes *N*-terminus of endogenous analgesic peptides⁹, in the present communication we report the mixed ligand complex formation tendency of six phenylalanine and tyrosine containing dipeptides, viz. glycyl-L-phenylalanine (glyphe), L-phenylalanineglycine (phegly), glycyl-L-tyrosine (glytyr), L-tyrosylglycine (tyrgly), L-phenylalanine-L-tyrosine (phetyr) and L-tyrosyl-L-phenylalanine (tyrphe) (B) with Cu^{II} in presence of unsubstituted imidazole (A).

Table 1. Stability constants for the proton and binary complexes of Cu^{II}-dipeptide/imidazole (B) binary systems

Temp. = 37°, I = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Parameter	Ligand B								
	glyphe	phegly	glytyr	tyrgly	phetyr	tyrphe	Glycylglycine ^a	Glycinamide ^a	Imidazole ^b
log β _{HB}	8.03(5)	7.21(6)	7.84(4)	7.82(7)	7.07(3)	7.22(4)	7.99(1)	7.89(1)	6.95(2)
log β _{HB}	10.90(7)	10.54(8)	10.66(6)	10.19(10)	10.45(4)	10.62(5)	11.26(1)	–	–
log β _{CuB}	–	5.39(5)	–	5.03(9)	5.62(6)	5.87(8)	5.70(8)	5.53(5)	4.21(9)
log β _{CuBH₁}	1.89(2)	1.31(2)	1.62(3)	1.20(3)	1.78(3)	1.92(4)	1.62(2)	-1.14(9)	–
log β _{CuB₂H₁}	5.12(7)	–	4.63(14)	4.25(10)	4.59(11)	5.11(12)	5.50(10)	3.18(9)	–
pK _{CuB} ^{II}	–	4.08	–	3.83	3.84	3.95	4.08	6.67	–
log K _{CuB₂H₁} ^{CuB}	–	–	–	-0.78	-1.03	-0.76	-0.20	2.35	–
log β _{CuBH₁} minus log K _{CuB₂H₁} ^{CuB}	–	–	–	1.98	2.81	2.68	1.82	1.21	–
log CuB ₂	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	7.55(14)
log CuB ₃	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10.73(16)
log CuB ₄	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	12.91(24)

Imidazole becomes ligand A in mixed ligand systems.

^aRef. 10, ^bRef. 11.

The significance of metal complexes of imidazoles becomes more obvious by considering the π -acceptor property of imidazole ring and the availability of the donor group in imidazole at physiological pH. All the studies were carried out by pH-titrimetry at 37° and $I = 0.15 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, and for selective systems the electronic spectral measurements have also been carried out. The above six Cu^{II}-dipeptide (B) binary systems have also been investigated under the present experimental conditions.

Results and Discussion

Cu^{II}-dipeptide (B) binary systems :

Various binary species detected in the title systems are reported in Table 1. The $\log \beta_{\text{CuB}}$ values of Cu^{II}-phegly, tyrgly, phetyr and pyrph systems are comparable to that in Cu^{II}-glyglycine system¹⁰, after taking into account for the difference in basicities of the ligands. This demonstrates that in the CuB species in the title systems, the dipeptide ligand binds the metal ion via *N*-amino and *O*-peptide groups as in the CuB glycylglycine species.

The CuBH₋₁ species has been detected in all the title binary systems. The $\text{p}K_{\text{CuB}}^{\text{H}}$ values (Table 1) are ~2.8 log units lesser compared to that in the Cu^{II}-glycinamide (B) system¹⁰, indicating the formation of a tridentate chelate via *N*-amino, *N*-peptido and *O*-carboxylato groups in the CuBH₋₁ species in the title systems. This can be further confirmed by noting that the λ_{max} values of 631 and 622 nm for the CuBH₋₁ species respectively in the Cu^{II}-phegly and glytyr (B) systems bear favourable comparison with that of 626 nm in the Cu^{II}-glycylglycine system, but are lesser than that of 676 nm in the Cu^{II}-glycinamide system. This shows that the coordination of the amide deprotonated dipeptide (B) in the CuBH₋₁ species in the Cu^{II}-phegly, glytyr and glycylglycine (B) systems results in a higher ligand field strength compared to that in the Cu^{II}-glycinamide (B) system, i.e. in the former systems the amide deprotonated dipeptide is tridentate. The absence of an additional peak, which is characteristic of Cu^{II}-phenolate ligation in the Cu^{II}-glytyr (B) system indicates that the OH group of glytyr ligand does not take part in bonding in its CuBH₋₁ species.

Cu^{II}-imidazole (A)-dipeptide (B) mixed ligand complex systems :

The various mixed ligand complexes identified in the title systems in their best-fit computer models using SCOGS computer program¹⁴ are given in Table 2.

CuAB species has been detected in the mixed ligand systems with B = phegly and glytyr. The $\log K_{\text{CuAB}}^{\text{CuB}}$ and $\log K_{\text{CuAB}}^{\text{CuA}}$ values in the Cu^{II}-imidazole (A)-phegly (B) system are comparable to the $\log K_1$ values respectively in the

Cu^{II}-imidazole and Cu^{II}-phegly binary systems (Table 1). This demonstrates monodentate binding of imidazole (A) via *N*-imidazole, and bidentate binding of phegly (B) via *N*-amino and *O*-peptide atoms in the CuAB species, similar to their binding in their respective binary species. The comparable $\log \beta_{\text{CuAB}}$ values in the mixed ligand systems with B = glytyr and phegly (Table 2) show that in the CuAB species in the former system imidazole is monodentate and glytyr is bidentate.

Table 2. Stability constants for the mixed ligand Cu^{II}-imidazole (A)-dipeptide (B) systems

Parameter	Dipeptides					
	glyphe	phegly	glytyr	tyrgly	phetyr	tyrphc
$\log \beta_{\text{CuAB}}$	–	10 08(9)	10 58(6)	–	–	–
$\log \beta_{\text{CuABH}_{-1}}$	5 69(5)	5 41(4)	5 29(8)	–	–	5 95(9)
$\log \beta_{\text{CuA}_2\text{B}}$	–	–	14 84(10)	14 87(8)	15 67(4)	15 81(10)
$\log \beta_{\text{CuA}_2\text{BH}_{-1}}$	8 46(11)	7 07(11)	8 49(8)	8 54(8)	9 40(4)	9 31(9)
$\text{p}K_{\text{CuAB}}^{\text{H}}$	–	4 67	5 29	–	–	–
$\text{p}K_{\text{CuA}_2\text{B}}^{\text{H}}$	–	–	6.35	6 33	6 27	6 50
$\log K_{\text{CuAB}}^{\text{CuB}}$	–	4 69	–	–	–	–
$\log K_{\text{CuAB}}^{\text{CuA}}$	–	5 87	6 37	–	–	–
$\log K_{\text{CuA}_2\text{B}}^{\text{CuA}}$	–	–	4 26	–	–	–
$\log K_{\text{CuABH}_{-1}}^{\text{CuA}}$	1 48	1 20	1 08	–	–	1 74
$\log K_{\text{CuABH}_{-1}}^{\text{CuB}}$	3 80	4 10	3 67	–	–	4 03
$\Delta \log K_{\text{CuABH}_{-1}}$	–0 41	–0 11	–0 54	–	–	–0 18

Above pH 4.5, the dipeptide (B) ligand in the CuAB species undergoes deprotonation and forms CuABH₋₁ and this species has been detected in the mixed ligand complex systems with B = glyphe, phegly, glytyr and tyrphc. The $\log \beta_{\text{CuABH}_{-1}}$ values (Table 2) bear favourable comparison with that of 5.65 in the Cu^{II}-imidazole (A)-glycylglycine (B) system⁷, wherein the CuABH₋₁ species, A is monodentate and (BH₋₁) binds the metal ion in a tridentate mode via *N*-amino, *N*-peptido and *O*-carboxylato atoms. This indicates that in the CuABH₋₁ species in the title mixed ligand systems, the amide deprotonated (BH₋₁) is tridentate. This is supported by the observation that λ_{max} values of 612, 610 and 610 nm for the CuABH₋₁ species respectively in the systems involving glycylglycine, glyphe and tyrphc (B) are comparable to each other. Again, the comparable $\log \beta_{\text{CuABH}_{-1}}$ values in the systems with B = glyphe and glytyr show that OH group of glytyr does not involve in ligation.

The $\Delta \log K_{\text{CuABH}_{-1}}$ ($= \log \beta_{\text{CuABH}_{-1}} - \log \beta_{\text{CuA}} - \log \beta_{\text{CuBH}_{-1}}$) values are more positive compared to the statistically expected value⁹, demonstrating marked stabilities for the CuABH₋₁ species compared to the binary analogs, CuA or CuBH₋₁.

The CuA₂B species has been detected in the mixed

ligand systems with B = glytyr, tyrgly, phetyr and tyrphe. The $\log K_{\text{CuA}_2\text{B}}^{\text{CuAB}}$ value of 4.26 in the glytyr (B) system is comparable to the $\log K_1$ value of 4.21 in the Cu^{II} -imidazole binary system¹¹, indicating that second imidazole (A) ligand also binds the metal ion in a monodentate manner in the CuA_2B species. Thus the water molecule in the fourth position of the CuAB species is replaced by the second imidazole (A) ligand in this CuA_2B species. The trends in the $\log \beta_{\text{CuA}_2\text{B}}$ values in the mixed ligand systems with B = glytyr, tyrgly, phetyr and tyrphe also indicate that both imidazole (A) ligands are monodentate and the dipeptides (B) are bidentate, giving a coordination number of 4 to the metal ion.

Above pH 5.5, the dipeptide ligand in the CuA_2B species undergoes deprotonation and forms $\text{CuA}_2\text{BH}_{-1}$ species. The $\text{p}K_{\text{CuA}_2\text{B}}^{\text{H}}$ values of 6.35, 6.33, 6.27 and 6.50, respectively, in the mixed ligand systems with B = glytyr, tyrgly, phetyr and tyrphe are lesser than that of 7.11 in the Cu^{II} -imidazole (A)-glycinamide (B) system⁷, indicating a tridentate mode of binding of (BH_{-1}) in the former four systems. However, these values are higher than that of 5.52 in the Cu^{II} -imidazole (A)-glycylglycine (B) system⁷, where (BH_{-1}) is tridentate. These trends show that the tridentate binding of (BH_{-1}) in the $\text{CuA}_2\text{BH}_{-1}$ species in the title systems exists only to an appreciable extent. The comparable $\log \beta_{\text{CuA}_2\text{BH}_{-1}}$ values in the glyphe and glytyr (B) systems show that OH group in glytyr (B) is not involved in bonding.

Fig. 1. Species distribution diagram for Cu^{II} -imidazole (A)-tyrpe (B) system at a Cu-A-B ratio of 1 : 2 : 2 : (1) unbound Cu^{II} , (2) CuB , (3) CuBH_{-1} , (4) $\text{CuB}_2\text{H}_{-1}$, (5) CuABH_{-1} , (6) CuA_2B , (7) $\text{CuA}_2\text{BH}_{-1}$. Curves for CuA , CuA_2 , CuA_3 and CuA_4 are not presented because of their very low concentrations.

The species distribution diagrams of the title ternary systems have been obtained for both 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 : 2 solutions. Formation of CuAB species occurs at pH 3.5 and has a maximum concentration in the pH region 4.5–5.0. The CuBH_{-1} binary species is the major species in all the mixed ligand systems in both 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 : 2 solutions in the pH region 4.5–5.0. The CuABH_{-1} species is formed above pH 4, and in some systems, even a maximum of 70% of the Cu^{II} has been found to be present in its form. Both the CuA_2B and $\text{CuA}_2\text{BH}_{-1}$ species are found to be predominant in the 1 : 2 : 2 solutions. In order to demonstrate the qualitative trends, the diagram obtained in the 1 : 2 : 2 solution of Cu^{II} -imidazole (A)-tyrpe (B) system is given in Fig. 1.

Experimental

All the ligands were extra pure Sigma products. The metal perchlorate and other reagents were prepared and estimated as described earlier¹¹. The apparatus and pH-titration procedure are described elsewhere^{12,13}. The auxiliary data in Cu^{II} -imidazole (A) system were taken from literature¹¹ (Table 1). All the calculations were done using SCOGS computer program¹⁴ on a NEXUS XT4AT6 computer.

The absorption spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 3B spectrophotometer as described earlier¹³. The spectral measurements were recorded at the particular pH where the concentrations of the particular species were found to be maximum as shown by the distribution plots.

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